

Experimental study on the drag reduction of a 3D bluff body by rotary plates

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We perform an experimental study on the turbulent flow around a squareback Ahmed body of height, h , at varying $Re = u_\infty h / \nu \in [0.5, 1] \times 10^5$, where u_∞ is the freestream velocity and ν is the incoming flow kinematic viscosity, under different yaw angles $\beta = (0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ)$, to analyze the use of rear flexibly-hinged parallel plates as a control strategy to reduce the drag. The model implements rear parallel rigid flaps of depth $d = 0.5h$, which are mounted with a torsional joint through embedded flexible foils of calibrated thickness. This holding system restricts the motion of the plates to rotary displacement, θ . The fluid-structure dynamics is characterized by the reduced velocity, defined as $U^* = u_\infty / f_n h$, where f_n is the natural frequency of rotary oscillations of the hinged plates, measured in free decay tests of flaps. In fact, we have explored the range of reduced velocity, $U^* = [0, 65]$, varying u_∞ and consequently Re . We perform force and pressure measurements to quantify the variations of the drag and the base pressure coefficients while laser displacement sensors are used to obtain the angular flaps motion. Results show that the hinged plates decrease the drag coefficient of the original body by nearly 4.4% for flow conditions aligned with the body axis. Under cross-flow conditions, their efficiency is even larger, attaining relative reductions drag of nearly 9.1% at $\beta = 10^\circ$ (13.5% in comparison with a body with fixed rigid plates of the same length). Such variations are shown to be associated to a passive reconfiguration process of rear flaps. Additionally, hinged flaps are shown to interact with Reflectional-Symmetry-Breaking (RSB) modes, typically present in the wake of three-dimensional bodies. The interaction with the RSB modes is characterized by two regimes, in such a way that the hinged flaps manage to suppress bi-stable behavior at low values of U^* (in a similar manner to rigid flaps), while they respond dynamically to switches between deflected states of the RSB modes, deviating themselves accordingly at high values of U^* .

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent international context has raised significant environmental and economic concerns related to energy consumption and associated greenhouse emission gases. Heavy road transport industry represents a major source of CO₂ emissions, due to their associated aerodynamically inefficient blunt geometry, which favors energy consumption. Hence, research on drag reduction, aiming to enhance fuel efficiency, may help developing effective strategies to render transport more sustainable and achieve environmental goals in the short term.

The drag experienced by a vehicle in motion is mainly constituted of pressure drag and friction drag. For a blunt based simplified vehicle, e.g. truck, the pressure drag may represent up to 85% of the total drag. Ahmed *et al.* [1] also found that the rear end contributes as much as 91% to the total pressure drag and is especially predominant at high speeds, as reported by Hucho and Sovran [2]. Furthermore, it is estimated that approximately 25% of the aerodynamic drag resistance of a heavy vehicle in real conditions is connected to its rear end [3]. Consequently, most of the flow control strategies developed over the past years, have been mainly designed to act on the flow separation at the rear end of the vehicle and the near-wake region [4].

The complex geometries of road vehicles are usually

simplified for research and academic studies, while preserving the main features of the flow and aerodynamics characterizing real vehicles. For instance, the model proposed by Ahmed *et al.* [1] has been extensively studied in their two versions: with a slanted trailing edge or with a square-back geometry. In the present study, we focus on the square-back Ahmed body, whose aerodynamics has been extensively described in [5–9]. This model features a large drag on account of the massive flow separation at the rear edges, that creates a large recirculating region associated to low pressure. Besides, the presence of Reflectional-Symmetry-Breaking (RSB) modes characterizes the asymmetry and dynamics of the near wake [7]. Under typical wind tunnel conditions, RSB modes dynamics is characterized by the stochastic switching between two horizontal symmetrically deflected positions of the wake for the Ahmed body. These modes induce additional side force on the body and an increase in drag [8], as they impact the base pressure distribution, so that the control strategies may be designed to retrieve wake symmetry by partially stabilizing the RSB modes.

Among other different strategies, applying a rear cavity to the base of the geometry by extending plates from the base of the geometry, is one way to reduce the drag [4] and manipulate the aforementioned RSB modes. When applied perpendicular to the base, they are effective on simplified geometries at aligned flow conditions

[10], yielding up to an 9% drag reduction due to the increase of the base pressure.

However, road vehicles often operate under cross-flow conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate forces and flow features of simplified heavy vehicle models over wide ranges of the yaw angle, β , which accounts for the misalignment of the model with respect to the incident freestream. The presence of side wind can significantly alter the flow detachment and the near wake properties, thus leading to the increase of side and drag forces, and the vehicle's instability [2]. In particular, typical studies of cross-wind are focused on the range given by $\beta \in [-10^\circ, 10^\circ]$, which are representative limits of the yaw angle for typical driving conditions [2, 11], and are in line with the new requirements for vehicles testing in the European Union.

In this regard, Howell *et al.* [12] highlighted the importance of these studies by presenting several real vehicles with a very similar drag coefficient at $\beta = 0^\circ$ yaw, that had a very different drag response to crosswind. Also, Fan *et al.* [13] analyzed the effect of yawed conditions on the pressure distribution and RSB modes on the square-back Ahmed body, indicating a strong effect on the horizontal and vertical base pressure gradients.

In terms of control strategies, Lorite-Díez *et al.* [14] showed that the performance of a straight cavity as drag reducer is dramatically decreased under cross-flow conditions. There, they proposed the use of a curved cavity (whose profile was obtained by means of previous shape optimization in two-dimensional flows [15]), that improves the effect of a straight cavity under aligned and yawed conditions. Other authors have also analyzed the performance of different symmetric control and drag reduction devices under cross-flow, such as boat-tailing [16] or pulsed jets actuators [17], showing a good capacity to reduce the drag.

Additionally, some recent studies have investigated the influence of asymmetric drag reduction devices with side wind conditions using tapering or lateral flaps [18–20]. In particular, as reported by [19], symmetric configurations of flaps do not provide optimal drag reductions under yawed conditions. In the contrary, largest reductions are obtained for different angle of deflection. Similar observations were made by [21], who used surrogate model-based algorithm to define optimal flaps orientations under aligned and yawed conditions for a blunt-base vehicle model. They showed that optimising the angle of each flap individually, under cross-flow conditions, can lower drag by enforcing the near wake symmetry through weakening of the large leeward side vortex. However, these optimization processes previously require, in general, to experimentally perform a detailed parametric study to collect a large amount of data for a given flow regime.

An alternative might consist in the exploration of self adaptive systems of flaps that allows dynamic reorientation under changing flow conditions and regimes. Thus, following this idea, and inspired in biological applications of reconfiguration processes involving flexible or movable

Figure 1. Sketch of the experimental set-up.

parts [22–24], we propose to analyze the performance of flexibly-hinged flaps that adapt to flow conditions dynamically. Previous analyses of two-dimensional or extruded blunt-bodies implementing flexible plates at the rear edges [25–27], show the ability of flaps to render the trailing edge more aerodynamic, and therefore, decrease the drag. This is an appealing approach, which remains barely unexplored in three-dimensional blunt-based vehicles, to the best of the authors' knowledge, and will be undertaken in the present work.

The paper is organized as follows: the problem description and experimental details are introduced in Sect. II. Next, Sect. III is devoted to analyze the results, comparing force, pressure and hinged-plates angular displacement measurements obtained with the different configurations. In particular, we first describe in Sect. III A the drag evolution and its modification mechanism for the tested configurations under aligned and crosswind conditions. Then, lateral aerodynamic loads, particularly important in this problem, are discussed in III B. The role of the lateral flaps and specially, the effect of hinged flaps in terms of RSB modes interaction is presented in Sect. III C. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Sect. IV.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

A. Experimental description

We study experimentally the turbulent wake behind a square-back Ahmed body of length $l = 261$ mm, width $w = 97.25$ mm and height $h = 72$ mm as in [28]. The model is placed inside a recirculating wind tunnel, available at the University of Jaén, with a nozzle of 8:1 contraction ratio connected to a 400×400 mm² test section, where turbulent intensity of the flow is around 1%.

Figure 2. (a) Detail of the flexibly-hinged flap system. (b) Instantaneous angular displacement θ of the flap from a free-decay test.

In the present work the Reynolds number varies in the range $Re = \rho_f u_\infty h / \mu_f = [48000, 96000]$, and three different yaw angles $\beta = [0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ]$ are studied to account for variable cross-wind. Here, u_∞ denotes the free-stream velocity, and ρ_f and μ_f the fluid density and viscosity respectively. The yaw angle is set by means of an automated turntable that allows a precise rotational placement of the model with an accuracy of 0.01° (Fig. 1). Similarly, the ground clearance is precisely set to $c/h = 0.278$ ($c = 20$ mm). The model associated blockage is 4% at aligned conditions and 6.5 % at $\beta = 10^\circ$.

Here, we study the influence of two flexibly-hinged rigid plates of depth $d = 0.5 h$ that are mounted at the lateral rear edges of the model. This flexible hinged flap is composed of a thin metallic foil (steel) of calibrated thickness $e_f/h = 3.5 \times 10^{-4}$ and a rigid plate of thickness $e_s/h = 6.9 \times 10^{-3}$ and density ρ_s (Fig. 2a). When mounted together at the base of the model, using a 3d printed part, the system behaves as an angular oscillator of one degree-of-freedom, with effective torsional stiffness k , damping ζ and mass moment of inertia J .

An illustration of a typical free-decay test is shown in Fig. 2(b), where the instantaneous angular displacement with respect to the centre of rotation $\theta(t)$ is depicted, along with its corresponding instantaneous fluctuating amplitude $\hat{\theta}(t)$ or envelope (which can be computed e.g. by applying the Hilbert transform). The natural frequency f_n of the system is easily obtained from the oscillation cycles, whereas the damping ratio ξ is determined from the envelope's exponential function $e^{-2\pi f_n \xi}$ (note that the structural damping may be obtained as $\zeta = 4\xi\pi f_n J$). The free-decay test parameters are obtained after performing 6 independent runs with an uncertainty below ± 0.1 Hz for f_n and ± 0.0007 for the damping ratio.

The fluid-structure interaction problem is then defined by means of the non-dimensional mass ratio of the system, $m^* = \rho_s / \rho_f \simeq 6250$, the combined mass-damping

parameter $\xi m^* \simeq 80$, and the reduced velocity,

$$U^* = \frac{u_\infty}{f_n h}, \quad (1)$$

which quantifies the dimensionless stiffness.

In view of that, the dimensionless stiffness of the hinged system can be easily changed by varying the free-stream velocity without modifying the experimental foil-flap arrangement. By doing so, the Reynolds number Re does not remain constant, however, the aerodynamic effect provided by the variation of the velocity u_∞ can be analyzed by studying initially the features of the reference model without hinged flaps. That said, results from three different configurations will be presented in the present work, namely: case B - baseline Ahmed body without any rear device; case RF - Ahmed body implementing static rigid flaps of depth $d = 0.5h$, i.e. $U^* \rightarrow 0$, and finally, case HF - Ahmed body implementing flexible hinged flaps of $d = 0.5h$ depicted in Fig. 2(a).

B. Forces, base pressure and plates displacement measurements

Force, pressure and displacement measurements were performed synchronously during experiments under controlled conditions. Several runs were defined for each test case in order to ensure repeatability of results.

The aerodynamic forces along the local coordinate axes, i.e. drag force f_x , side force f_y and lift force f_z , were measured using a precision six-axis load cell, connected to the model through four cylindrical supports (Fig. 1), so the balance is rotated with the body, fixing the coordinate system with the vehicle model. The dimensionless force coefficients are then obtained as,

$$c_i = \frac{2 f_i}{\rho_f u_\infty^2 h w}, \quad (2)$$

where c_x and c_y , c_z are the drag and lateral force coefficients. The force measurements produce an associated uncertainty below ± 0.001 for $c_{x,y}$.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the base pressure was measured with help of taps distributed in a 3×3 equispaced grid with $\Delta y = 0.26h$ mm and $\Delta z = 0.18h$, providing with local pressure values p_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 9$). The acquisition was performed by means of a 64-channel pressure scanner with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz providing an accuracy of 0.6Pa per channel. Base pressure measurements will be expressed in terms of the non-dimensional pressure coefficient as

$$c_{p,i} = \frac{p_i - p_\infty}{\rho_f u_\infty^2 / 2}, \quad (3)$$

where p_∞ is the free-stream pressure, registered using a Pitot tube placed upstream of the model. The uncertainty associated to $c_{p,i}$ values is below ± 0.001 in the

present experiments. In addition, the base drag coefficient [29] will be estimated by means of

$$c_B = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n c_{p,i} \quad (4)$$

being $n = 9$ the total number of base pressure taps. Besides, following previous studies [see e.g. 7, 14] the wake asymmetry can be quantified with help of the horizontal and vertical pressure gradients, i.e. g_y and g_z , calculated as

$$g_y = h \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial y} \simeq \frac{1}{2} h \left[\frac{c_{p,6} - c_{p,4}}{y_6 - y_4} \right], \quad (5)$$

$$g_z = h \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial y} \simeq \frac{1}{2} h \left[\frac{c_{p,8} - c_{p,2}}{y_8 - y_2} \right]. \quad (6)$$

Finally, the displacement of the rear flaps was recorded by means of optical laser sensors model (see Fig. 1). These sensors measured the linear displacement of the flaps' tips, from which, after application of adequate trigonometric transformation, the instantaneous angular location θ was obtained. The linear resolution provided by the laser translates into an angular accuracy of 0.0005 rad. Note that counter-clockwise rotations are considered positive while clockwise rotations are negative (see Fig.1).

In the following, time-dependent variables will be denoted using lower-case letters a , while time-averaged values will be expressed by means of upper-case letters $A = \bar{a}$. In addition, \hat{a} will denote instantaneous fluctuating amplitude of the variable a , which will be computed by means of the Hilbert transform, so that \hat{A} will represent the corresponding time-averaged fluctuating amplitude.

C. Drag decomposition

Since the drag is defined as the aerodynamic force component along the body axis, all pressure forces on lateral surfaces (i.e.: having wall normal directions perpendicular to this axis) do not contribute to the drag, whatever the yaw is. This is the case for the 4 sides of the baseline body and for the rigid plates from RF configuration. However, these surfaces still contribute to the drag through friction. Our drag, C_x , and base drag, C_B , measurements allow the following drag decomposition:

$$C_x = C_B + C_R, \quad (7)$$

where C_R is a coefficient that comprises all the drag contributions except the body base one such as the body supports, the frictional drag on the 4 lateral body sides

and the body nose. It also accounts for the flaps when they are added. Therefore, it is possible to assess the drag contribution of the flaps assuming that between the body with flaps (RF or HF configurations) and the baseline (B configuration), the drag contributions due to the nose, the supports and the four lateral sides are the same at a given yaw. That assumption can be reasonable since the only body surfaces that could be sensitive to the flaps presence are the rear part of the four lateral sides. As they only contribute through friction, they are known to be a small contributor to drag [1] at the tested Re . Under this assumption, $\Delta C_R = \Delta C_x - \Delta C_B$ can be seen as the direct drag contribution of the aerodynamic force exerted on the flaps, where we remind that the difference Δ is operated from the baseline.

III. SEC:RESULTS

A. Drag reduction

We first present results from time-averaged drag C_x , base drag C_B and C_R coefficients and their evolution with the Reynolds number for the baseline Ahmed body (denoted case B) at different tested yaw angles β in Fig.3. Regardless of the value of β , C_x is reduced when Re increases, as the friction drag is reduced (see Fig.3a). In fact, Fig. 3(b) shows that the pressure drag, estimated here by means of C_B , does not depend on Re for any yaw orientation. The remaining body drag, expressed by C_R , is reduced when Re increases as it compromises the friction drag.

Besides, both drag and base drag coefficients increase as the yaw angle of the body with respect to the streamwise direction grows. Lorite-Díez *et al.* [14] reported a linear variation between C_x (or C_B) with β , indicating that the drag coefficient increases with the yaw angle due to a decrease in the base pressure associated with a shorter recirculation region. Such variation might be also related to the flow separation observed along the longitudinal edges of the Ahmed body [30]. Although these streamwise vortices are not investigated herein, their contribution to the drag at yaw are naturally integrated in the measured base suction and force coefficients.

The same linear variation between drag and yaw angle can be inferred from Fig. 3. Also, note that the values of C_x and C_B obtained in the present work are in good agreement with results previously reported for similar set-ups [14, 31]. Interestingly, C_R decreases with yaw which might be due to the thrust produced by the pressure loading around the body nose at yaw reported by [13] for the Ahmed body.

The values of the time-averaged drag coefficients featured by the baseline model will be used as reference in Fig.4 to illustrate the effect of the rigid (RF case) and hinged flaps (HF case) on the body drag for the Reynolds numbers tested, and the corresponding range of reduced velocity U^* for the flexible flaps arrangement. The ref-

erence values and the respective relative reductions of drag, base drag and remaining drag coefficient are listed in Table I.

That said, under aligned flow conditions, $\beta = 0^\circ$, the RF configuration reduces efficiently the base drag C_B by approximately $\Delta C_B \simeq -12\%$ for all the tested values of Re . However, drag reductions are small, being the largest variation $\Delta C_x \simeq -1.9\%$. This may stem from the fact that, when the flaps are mounted, the body surface increases and so does the friction drag, and consequently, C_R , what offsets the reduction given by C_B .

On the other hand, the use of hinged flaps (HF configuration) reduces more efficiently the base drag C_B , although, again, the drag improvement is smaller, likely due to a larger friction drag contribution (see Fig. 4 c). Nevertheless, a significant drag reduction is obtained ($\Delta C_x \simeq -4.1\%$) which is approximately constant over the tested range of Re or reduced velocity U^* (see Fig. 4). This improvement attained with respect to the rigid (RF) configuration may be presumably caused by the reconfiguration of flaps occurring when a degree of freedom is introduced with the flexible foil.

Under yawed conditions, the RF configuration is neither capable to reduce C_x nor C_B with respect to the baseline Ahmed body. Their increase, especially at 10° , must be related to the strong separations at the top and bottom edges of the flaps. In terms of the rest of the body, yaw angle seems to have very little influence on ΔC_R for the RF configuration.

On the other hand, the hinged flaps (HF) feature increasing reductions of base drag and drag with growing values of U^* (larger relative flexibility) for both $\beta = 5^\circ$ and 10° , which may be conveniently used in practical applications to reduce drag under cross-wind conditions. In particular, very similar values of ΔC_B are obtained for both yaw angle values when the HF configuration is set (the obtained changes with respect to base configuration can be seen in Table I). However, the drag coefficient reduction, which is larger than that of the base drag C_B , increases with the growing value of β (see Fig.4b), reaching maximum relative improvements of $\Delta C_x \simeq -7.5\%$ at $\beta = 5^\circ$ and $\Delta C_x \simeq -9.1\%$ at $\beta = 10^\circ$ (see Table I). These results suggest that there is a progressive reconfiguration of the flexible flaps with U^* and β , that contributes to reduce drag. In this regard, HF is able to produce negative values of C_R (see Fig. 4c), so, hinged flaps may produce some thrust on the body, which increases with yaw.

In fact, the hinged flaps may also weaken the strength of vortices originated around the body, which are known to increase the drag [30, 32], thus reducing their impact on C_x and providing the additional drag reduction observed here when compared with the trend of ΔC_B . Nevertheless, one can conjecture that the relative contribution of these longitudinal vortices to the drag force increases with β , and the stronger reconfiguration at large Re or U^* may lead to higher potential for aerodynamic improvement. This is in line with our results, since the slope of ΔC_x vs U^* is greater than that observed for

ΔC_B at yawed conditions. That said, in order to better understand the role of reconfiguration, we next discuss the relationship between C_B , C_x and Θ .

Figure 5 displays the evolution of time-averaged flaps deflection Θ , referred here as positive (resp. negative) in the inwards (resp. outwards) direction, with respect to the reduced velocity (note that for the sake of conciseness, amplitude of angular fluctuations $\hat{\Theta}$ are not depicted, as its value lies always below the 15% of the average displacement Θ within the range of U^* and β investigated here, and therefore, reconfiguration can be considered quasi-static at first order). Initially the flaps are slightly oriented outwards in our experiment due to small pre-charges in the setup (below 1°). Nonetheless, the fluid load is able to gradually move them inwards without remarkable influence of the initial position. For aligned flow conditions, $\beta = 0$, the lateral flaps reconfigure inwards, depicting a linear trend, as the pressure gradient at their sides suggests. A maximum reconfiguration angle, of approximately 3° , is reached at the highest U^* (see Fig. 5a). Both flaps deflect inwards nearly symmetrically, with differences below 0.5° for any U^* value.

The reconfiguration of the flaps remains below the typical separation angles (above 12°), then, the flow massive separation may occur at their trailing edge. Besides, the role of the recirculating region bluntness in the horizontal direction, H_r (defined as the distance between flaps trailing edges non-dimensionalized by the width of the body base, w) on the drag and base drag changes is analyzed with help of Fig. 5(b,c). For aligned conditions, ΔC_x is not correlated with H_r while C_B is, suggesting that the base pressure recovery is governed by the flaps reconfiguration, however, the additional friction drag cancels out the contribution of ΔC_B on ΔC_x .

At yawed conditions, the flaps may deflect asymmetrically as they face differently the incoming wind. At $\beta = 5^\circ$, the asymmetry is not so large and both flaps deflect in a similar way. Still, the windward flap deflection tends to compensate the yaw angle and aligns with the flow direction, while the inwards deflection of the leeward flap is even stronger. Their position is fairly similar at high U^* , confirming the small role of yaw on the flap deflection for $\beta = 5^\circ$. In fact, at this yaw angle, the flow dynamics at the forebody [32] and at the near wake [14] are not very far from those observed at aligned flow conditions.

At the higher value of yaw, $\beta = 10^\circ$, the leeward flap deflects strongly with U^* reaching values close to 20° while the windward flap rotates only slightly inwards with increasing U^* . This result seems to be connected to the structure of the recirculation regions for a yawed Ahmed described in [14]. In the windward side, the flow is not deflected and its evolution is almost potential while the large recirculating region is fixed on the leeward side. Then, the pressure gradient between both sides of the flaps is greater at the leeward than at the windward side. In addition, the three-dimensional topology of the streamwise vortices existing under yaw conditions is not

Config.	$\beta(^{\circ})$	C_x	$\Delta C_{x,B}(\%)$	C_B	$\Delta C_{B,B}(\%)$	C_R	$\Delta C_{R,B}(\%)$
B	0	0.380	-	0.176	-	0.204	-
	5	0.429	-	0.229	-	0.200	-
	10	0.482	-	0.286	-	0.196	-
RF	0	0.379	-0.3	0.155	-11.9	0.224	9.8
	5	0.436	1.6	0.230	0.4	0.206	3.0
	10	0.507	5.2	0.305	6.6	0.202	3.1
HF	0	0.364	-4.2	0.143	-18.8	0.221	8.3
	5	0.397	-7.5	0.197	-14.0	0.200	0.0
	10	0.438	-9.1	0.254	-11.2	0.184	-6.1

Table I. Drag, base drag and remaining drag coefficient values in each configuration (Base: B, Rigid flaps: RF, Hinged flaps: HF) for the tested yaw angles at $Re \sim 10^5$. Relative drag $\Delta C_{x,B}(\%)$, base drag $\Delta C_{B,B}(\%)$ and remaining drag $\Delta C_{R,B}(\%)$ changes with respect to B configuration are included.

symmetric in both leeward and windward sides [30]. The observed reconfiguration tries to adapt the flaps position to the topology of such recirculating region, shown in [14], i.e. the windward recirculating streamlines show small curvature with respect to Ahmed body windward side while the leeward recirculating streamlines show a strong curvature that increases with yaw. The asymmetry of the recirculating bubble induced by the yaw also acts on the unsteady flap response. Although the flaps reconfiguration is mostly quasi-static at first order for the range of U^* studied here, we can observe some differences between windward and leeward flaps oscillations, $\hat{\Theta}$. While the amplitude of the windward oscillations remain constant with U^* (around $\hat{\Theta} \sim 0.5$), that of the leeward flap vibration increases with U^* (largest values of $\hat{\Theta} \simeq 3$), confirming the aforementioned strong differences in the flaps-recirculating region interaction on both wake sides at $\beta = 10^{\circ}$. The different pressure gradient distributions at both sides of the flaps may also explain the obtained values of ΔC_R , in that sense, one can estimate the thrust produced by the flaps deflection with the torsional stiffness of the joint and the forcing location acting on the flap. Our results indicate a direct relation between that thrust and ΔC_R . Thus, increasing yaw provokes greater flaps' deflection, generating more thrust and therefore, reducing further C_B and C_x .

The reconfiguration of the flaps is effective to reduce the drag and the base drag at yawed conditions, as Figs. 5 (b,c) show. The base pressure recovery, ΔC_B , shows an excellent direct correlation with H_r , with a nearly constant slope for the orientations tested in our experiments. In terms of drag, the near wake bluntness correlates linearly with ΔC_x under yaw, although the slope increases with β . Thus, the flaps reconfiguration seems to be able to increase the base pressure and reduce the drag of the remaining parts of the body (mainly associated with the formation of three-dimensional streamwise vortices on the body edges), thus reducing efficiently the baseline body drag coefficient at yawed conditions. Also, as the yaw increases, their impact on the aerodynamic drag is seen to increase (see Figs. 4, 5).

B. Lateral forces

Our experiment facility allows us to obtain the lateral forces acting on the model too. At $\beta = 0^{\circ}$, Reflectional-Symmetry-Breaking (RSB) modes act on our baseline Ahmed body producing the appearance of two equally-probable horizontal asymmetric states that produce a significant lateral force [28]. To describe the amplitude of these modes in terms of lateral forces, one has to compute the averaged level of fluctuations of c_y signal, \hat{C}_y , since the averaged C_y will just dictate the probability of exploring one of the two asymmetric states [33]. Figure 6(a) shows the evolution of \hat{C}_y with the Reynolds number for the different rear configurations tested here. Case B depicts a lateral force, associated to RSB modes, with an amplitude around 0.02, which agrees with previously reported results.

When rigid lateral flaps (RF) are set, the lateral force amplitude is strongly decreased, suggesting a strong attenuation of RSB modes, as it happens with rigid rear full cavities [10]. More interestingly, hinged-flaps behave as rigid flaps at low Reynolds (low values of U^*) but \hat{C}_y amplitude grows as the free-stream velocity increases above an intermediate value, which will be shown to be related to excitation of flaps vibration by the RSB modes that defines a critical value of U^* for the fluid-structure interaction mechanism. In general, as U^* increases from there, the aerodynamic loading acting on the hinged flaps also increases (as inferred from the inwards flaps displacement shown in Fig. 5) above the value provided by the rigid static flaps. However, the lateral force \hat{C}_y associated with such region of U^* for the HF arrangement remains smaller than that experienced by the baseline Ahmed body, probably because the associated horizontal pressure gradient amplitude is smaller.

Once yaw conditions are set, the value of the time-averaged side force coefficient C_y is naturally affected, and becomes non nil, as the problem loses its symmetry (see Fig. 6 b,c). As shown in [33, 34], the value of C_y for the baseline Ahmed body varies linearly with β (for $|\beta| > 1$). This result is also obtained from

the present data, since the coefficient takes the values $C_y \simeq [0, 0.28, 0.56]$ at $\beta = 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ$ respectively for the case B. Adding the flaps (for RF and HF configurations) should increase the lateral force due to the increased length of the body, however, this effect is balanced by the reduction of the horizontal base pressure gradient, G_y , for both RF and HF in comparison with B configuration. Then, the measured side force coefficient does not change significantly with Re at $\beta = 5^\circ$, remaining nearly constant, providing a similar reduction of C_y with rigid and hinged flaps (around 8.3%).

For $\beta = 10^\circ$, cases B and RF show similar trends with Re , indicating that they exhibit an equivalent behaviour. Conversely, for the HF case, C_y depicts an increase with Re , suggesting that the aforementioned thrust induced by the torsional joint is also acting on the side force. Moreover, the strong deflection of the flaps at yawed conditions (specially at 10°) may reduce the lateral projected area in comparison with RF configuration, which partially explains the differences depicted in Fig. 6(c). The use of hinged flaps decreases the side loading, when compared to the other two configurations, as β grows, showing a general better aerodynamic performance of this system.

C. Bi-stable dynamics

In the present section, we will discuss the effect of the rear flaps on the bi-stable dynamics of the near wake with help of the base pressure measurements. Under symmetric conditions, our experiment presents RSB modes horizontal bi-stability, so, only $\beta = 0^\circ$ orientation is considered herein.

Fig. 7 presents respectively the contours of Probability Density Function (PDF) of the horizontal and vertical pressure gradients, g_y and g_z , against Re (or U^*) for the three configurations analyzed, baseline, rigid flaps and hinged flaps. As observed therein, the wake behind the reference case B exhibits, with the same probability, two states characterized by respective positive (P) and negative (N) values of g_y , and associated to the two horizontally deflected mirrored RSB states reported in [7]. As the figure depicts, this is the outcome of a time-evolution of g_y characterized by an intermittent random switching between negative and positive values, as depicted in Fig. 8(a), where the bi-stable dynamics is illustrated for $Re \simeq 10^5$.

Additionally, the vertical base pressure gradient g_z (Fig. 7b), remains positive along the whole range of Re , showing a slight increase in its value with Re , on account of the ground effect which decreases pressure at the bottom of the base. The bi-stable dynamics in the horizontal axis y and the slight increase of the wake asymmetry in the vertical axis z is also illustrated with help of the combined PDF in Figs. 7(g,i).

When the rigid flaps are installed, the wake is symmetrized and the RSB modes are stabilized. This can be

observed in the PDF of g_y (Fig. 7c) which now features a single peak with no trace of the bi-stable switching dynamics. The lateral rigid flaps move the separation point far from the body base and reduce the separated mixing layers interaction, which eliminates the RSB modes [9]. Their effect on the vertical asymmetry is weak, showing a slight sharpening of the peak (Fig. 7d).

Interestingly, the use of hinged flaps produces a hybrid wake behaviour between both previous dynamics. In particular, as depicted in Fig. 7(e), when the reduced velocity U^* (or Re) is small, the PDF of the horizontal gradient g_y covers a wider region of values, suggesting that the RSB mode explore different locations around a central plane. This means that the wake undergoes a sort of weak symmetrization and does not display a complete stabilization of the RSB modes, on account of the finite stiffness value of the flaps $U^* > 0$. Note that the rigid flaps correspond to the particular case $U^* \rightarrow 0$.

However, around $U^* \simeq 45$ the wake displays a transition towards a bi-stable behaviour, and g_y starts to explore again the two positive and negative values associated to P and N states of the RSB modes. The qualitative change between both regimes is clearly illustrated in the combined PDF (Fig. 7h,j). Interestingly, the flaps displacement is sensitive to such changes in the pressure gradient, and they fluctuate around a mean shifted location, following the switches of g_y , as shown in the corresponding PDF of fluctuating amplitude $\hat{\Theta}$ depicted in Fig. 8(b). There, two equi-probable branches of dynamic response can be observed for $\hat{\Theta}$ corresponding to P and N states.

Notwithstanding, the bi-stable dynamics is qualitatively different from that of the baseline case. As depicted in Fig. 8(a,b), the use of hinged flaps slows down the switching dynamics, as the time-evolution of g_y displays fewer switches between P and N states than that corresponding the baseline case. This effect is presumably induced by the inertia of flaps.

Additionally, the amplitude of g_y decreases when the flexible flaps are used compared to the baseline case (i.e. $|g_y|_{HF} \simeq 0.11$ vs. $|g_y|_B \simeq 0.19$). This demonstrates that the hinged flaps manage to attenuate the wake asymmetry even if the wake dynamics is still bi-stable, what leads to a smaller fluctuating amplitude of the side force \hat{C}_y , as discussed in Fig. 6.

The different bi-stable dynamics between both configurations is further illustrated in Fig. 8(d), which shows the non-dimensional number of switches between positive (P) and negative (N) values of g_y , N_s^* (computed as $N_s h / tu_\infty$), versus the U^* . Specifically, the number of switches has been computed by using a threshold of $|g_y| \geq 0.09$ to define RSB asymmetric states. Note that, as there are different horizontal pressure gradient amplitudes for asymmetric states in the two different configurations, a common robust threshold has been selected by means of statistic post-processing, thus allowing to quantitatively characterize and compare the bi-stable dynamics.

As expected, few switches are identified below the critical value of $U_{cr}^* \simeq 45$, whereas N^* increases progressively from there on, with the reduced velocity, as the relative stiffness of hinges decreases and the coupled fluid-structure dynamics speeds up (note that N^* is not zero below U_{cr}^* since the value of g_y explores a wide range of values as the centre of pressure meanders on the base, as illustrated in Fig. 7e). For the whole range of reduced velocity investigated, the number of switches for the baseline case remains above that of the hinged system, confirming the slower switching dynamics of the bi-stability as the flexible flaps are used.

Finally, as an additional comment, one may expect that, in view of these results, lighter flaps featuring lower mass-damping parameter ζm^* induce a stronger dynamic response, thus leading to bi-stable dynamics, even at low values of U^* , what could be detrimental from the control point of view.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of hinged lateral flaps (HF) as drag reducers has been tested in a squareback Ahmed body subject to turbulent flow with $Re \in [0.5, 1] \times 10^5$ under different yaw conditions. Their effect has been compared with baseline body (B) and equivalent lateral rigid flaps (RF) arrangement by means of force, pressure and deflection measurements in wind tunnel tests. For the range of parameters used herein, it has been found that the hinged flaps deflection is almost quasi-static at first order when the different flow conditions are set. They display a clear example of passive reconfiguration, which has been shown to be the key element to produce important modifications in the interaction between the turbulent flow field and the different rear ends. While the rigid flaps do not produce significant drag changes, even if they increase the base pressure, due to their additional length, the use hinged flaps manages to efficiently reduce both base drag and drag coefficients for aligned and yawed conditions. The mechanism of drag reduction is based on base pressure recovery, topology changes of streamwise vortices at the body edges and the effect of the flap deflection. Besides, their enhanced performance increases with Re and yaw

angle, suggesting an interesting potential in real applications.

In addition to aerodynamic changes, the employed configurations (B, RF and HF) interact differently with RSB modes at aligned conditions. The wake behind the baseline body depicts the classical bi-stable behaviour described in the literature. The rigid flaps are able to symmetrize the wake in the horizontal direction as closed cavities do. However, the hinged flaps configuration features two different dynamics behaviors as U^* increases. Thus, below a critical value of the reduced velocity $U^* < U_{cr}^*$, the hinged flaps behaves as rigid flaps, inducing symmetrization at the wake, without a clear trace of asymmetric deflected states (P or N) related to RSB modes. On the other hand, for $U^* > U_{cr}^*$, the hinged flaps deflect following changes in the horizontal pressure gradient given by the switches between RSB modes, thus describing a bi-stable behaviour, although characterized by slower dynamics with fewer changes. Under these conditions, the near wake and flaps are synchronized and they move accordingly. Such slowed motion is associated to the large inertia of the flaps given by the selected mass ratio parameter of the problem m^* . Interestingly, these slow oscillations of limited amplitude do not hinder much the side force fluctuations, as the value of \hat{C}_y remain smaller than that of the baseline case, once the bi-stable dynamics is triggered.

These combined advantages in terms of drag and side forces suggests an interesting potential for the use of hinged flaps in real applications with heavy vehicles, where passive reconfiguration may help improving the global aerodynamic and the adaptability of control systems to changing flow conditions. To that aim, precise design of the system and selection of fluid-structure interaction parameters, e.g. reduced velocity and mass-damping ratio, may be required to properly adapt the present solution to more realistic conditions.

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Figure 3. Evolution of the time-averaged drag, C_x , (a); base drag (b) and C_R coefficients with the Reynolds number for the baseline case (B, squares) at different yaw angles ($\beta = 0^\circ$ in blue, $\beta = 5^\circ$ in red and $\beta = 10^\circ$ in green).

Figure 4. Averaged base drag (a), drag (b) and remaining drag (c) coefficients relative change (ΔC_x , ΔC_B and ΔC_R , resp.) with respect to case B evolution with Reynolds number for RF (rigid flaps, diamonds) and HF (hinged flaps, circles) cases at different yaw angles ($\beta = 0^\circ$ in blue, $\beta = 5^\circ$ in red and $\beta = 10^\circ$ in green).

Figure 5. (a) Time-averaged flap inwards deflection (leeward and windward), Θ , evolution with reduced velocity, U^* , for all tested orientations. At $\beta = 0^\circ$, leeward, L , and windward, W , flap deflections have been averaged. (b,c) The recirculating region bluntness in the horizontal direction, H_r , correlation with averaged drag (b) and base drag (c) coefficients relative change (ΔC_x and ΔC_B , resp.) with respect to B configuration for all tested orientations. Solid lines depicting the associated linear fit are included.

Figure 6. Evolution of lateral C_y force coefficient with Re at different yaw angles: $\beta = 0^\circ$ (a), $\beta = 0^\circ$ (b) and $\beta = 10^\circ$ (c); for the tested configurations (B, RF, HF). In the case of aligned conditions, \hat{C}_y instead of C_y is depicted.

Figure 7. Evolution of the contours of the pressure gradients PDF of g_y , (a), (c), (e) and of g_z (b), (d), (f) with Reynolds number Re (and U^*), for the three configurations B, RF and HF. (g)-(j) Combined horizontal and vertical base pressure gradients PDF for selected values of Re for the B (top) and the HF (bottom) configurations. All PDFs are normalized with their corresponding maxima.

Figure 8. RSB dynamics at $\beta = 0^\circ$. (a, b) Temporal evolution of horizontal, vertical base pressure gradients and flap deflection angle for B and HF configurations at $Re \sim 10^5$. (c) PDF of the observed deflected angle position for HF configuration. The PDF is normalized with its maximum value. (d) Non-dimensional switching events, N_s^* , evolution with Re for B and HF configurations. Error bars are included for the different tests performed.